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O3; Laboratory report on solar/NSSM treatment of selected PFAS in batch reactor (2nd year) (D3.1)

Project: Solar-assisted photocatalytic degradation of perfluorinated compounds in water (*SoAPperF*), IPS-2002-02-4780.

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1. Experimental procedure for monitoring selected PFAS

PFOA (Perfluorooctanoic acid, CAS # 1763-23-1)

LC-MS analytical testing of PFOA

Due to the observed increase in the concentration of PFOA during the photocatalytic reactions, additional tests were conducted with the aim of establishing and eliminating analytical error.

Method linearity assessment

To determine the most favorable working range for PFOA concentration, linearity tests were performed across the following concentration ranges: 0.01–0.1 ppm, 0.1–1 ppm, and 1–10 ppm. The linear range should cover 0–150% of the expected analyte concentration. All standards were prepared using polypropylene laboratory dishes. Each concentration standard was aliquoted into three separate polypropylene vials. Samples were analyzed using LC-MS. The mean value for three separate injections of each concentration was extracted, and using the mean values obtained, graphs were plotted and the R^2 values were calculated. Linear approximation trend lines, forced through zero, were generated using Excel.

Table 1. Method linearity assessment.

Range 0.01-0.1 ppm		Range 0.1–1 ppm		Range 1–10 ppm ppm	
Concentration /ppm	Area	Concentration /ppm	Area	Concentration /ppm	Area
0.01	19765	0.1	195870	1	1251212
0.01	20245	0.1	201241	1	1237444
0.01	20257	0.1	203406	1	1254115
0.025	50434	0.25	434234	2.5	2272862
0.025	51025	0.25	434814	2.5	2295625
0.025	51539	0.25	432816	2.5	2279630
0.05	103302	0.5	757862	5	3479483
0.05	106242	0.5	776740	5	3491428
0.05	102801	0.5	772752	5	3504436
0.075	149749	0.75	1039762	7.5	4427396
0.075	151268	0.75	1038906	7.5	4403849
0.075	148651	0.75	1041326	7.5	4439002
0.1(D)	195731	1	1276566	10	5234006
0.1(D)	198229	1	1288875	10	5284153
0.1(D)	196804	1	1289611	10 ppm	5300029
R² = 0.9996		R² = 0.9925		R² = 0.9734	
R² = 0.9906				/	
/		R² = 0.9580			
R² = 0.9628					

Based on the R² values, the optimal concentration of PFOA for use in reactions was found to be 0.1 ppm, as the values from 0–150% of the specified concentration fall within the linear range.

Figure 1. Calibration curves in ranges: a) 0.01-0.1 ppm b) 0.1-1 ppm c) 0.01-1 ppm d) 1-10 ppm e) 0.1-10 ppm f) 0.01-10 ppm.

Figure 2. PFOA chromatogram

Figure 3. Count vs. Mass-to-Charge (m/z).

Figure 4. PFOA chromatogram with MRM transitions.

Laboratory dishes and vials material (glass versus polypropylene)

To assess the influence of laboratory dishes and vials material on PFOA concentration, standard solutions were prepared in concentration range 0.01-1 ppm. All standards were prepared using laboratory glassware. Each concentration standard was aliquoted into three separate glass vials. Samples were analyzed using LC-MS. Relative standard deviation (RSD) was calculated for each concentration level and compared with the results obtained by preparation and analysis in polypropylene (PP) dishes and vials. R^2 value was calculated to confirm linearity.

Table 2. Glass versus polypropylen vials and laboratory dishes test

PFOA concentration /ppm	Area (glass)	%RSD (glass)	Area (PP)	%RSD (PP)
0.01	19675	2.66067	19765	1.400551
0.01	20651		20245	
0.01	19791		20257	
0.025	44490	3.764212	50434	1.199321
0.025	45885		51025	
0.025	47940		51539	
0.05	99112	1.795025	103302	1.856021
0.05	102236		106242	
0.05	99132		102801	
0.075	153054	0.611772	149749	0.861178
0.075	151523		151268	
0.075	153214		148651	
0.1	193078	1.142443	195731	0.646826
0.1	191924		198229	
0.1	196202		196804	
0.25	471807	1.241469	434234	0.215311
0.25	476754		434814	
0.25	483609		432816	
0.5	888286	0.693361	757862	1.128998
0.5	876960		776740	
0.5	878647		772752	
0.75	1182711	0.187229	1039762	0.103914
0.75	1178449		1038906	
0.75	1181601		1041326	
1	1437207	0.542054	1276566	0.507749
1	1440559		1288875	
1	1452119		1289611	
R² value	R² = 0.9920		R² = 0.9906	

Based on the calculated RSD and R² values, it was confirmed that both glass and polypropylene dishes and vials are suitable for PFOA standard preparation and analysis.

Filter membrane material

Three different filter membrane materials were tested: nylon, cellulose acetate (CA), and hydrophilized polytetrafluoroethylene (H-PTFE). Their influence on PFOA concentration was examined during the first use and after reuse. Filters used for the first time were tested with the initially prepared solution, while reused filters were tested with a solution that had been exposed to solar light for 60 minutes. PFOA recovery was calculated with respect to the concentration value obtained without using a filter.

Table 3. First time used filters – membrane material comparison

Filter memb. material	c(PFOA)/ppm	Recovery
None	0.09588	/
CA	0.08969	93.54 %
Nylon	Not detected	NA
H-PTFE	0.59136	616.77 %

Table 4. Reused filters – membrane material comparison

Filter memb. material	c(PFOA)/ppm	Recovery
None	0.09739	/
CA	0.09669	99.28 %
Nylon	0.00666	6.84 %
H-PTFE	0.13313	136.70 %

The cellulose filter exhibited the best properties for filtering solutions containing PFOA.

Sampling position

The influence of the sampling position on the detected concentration was examined. During the reaction, samples were taken simultaneously from the bottom and top of the reactor. Percentage difference was calculated.

Table 5. Measured PFOA concentration in regard to sampling position

Time/min	Position of sampling	c(PFOA)/ppm	Percentage difference
t= -30	Bottom	0.09269	0.31 %
t= -30	Top	0.09298	
t=0	Bottom	0.09492	0.63 %
t=0	Top	0.09432	
t=60	Bottom	0.09782	0.44 %
t=60	Top	0.09739	
t=180	Bottom	0.11027	0.35 %
t=180	Top	0.10988	

Based on the calculated percentage difference, the sampling position does not have a significant influence on the detected concentration of PFOA.

Vial vortexing before injection

The influence of vortexing the vial before injecting the sample was tested, and the relative standard deviation (RSD) for 10 successive measurements was calculated.

Table 6. Vial vortexing before injection

Time/min	Vortexed c(PFOA)/ ppm	Not vortexed c(PFOA)/ ppm
t=10	0.09218	0.09181
t=20	0.09271	0.09248
t=30	0.09179	0.09153
t=40	0.09099	0.09148
t=50	0.09083	0.09423
t=60	0.0888	0.09226
t=70	0.09292	0.0926
t=80	0.09086	0.09357
t=90	0.09052	0.10034
t=100	0.08995	0.09299
%RSD:	1.397646516	2.800833531

Based on the calculated RSD, vortexing the vial before injection increases the precision of the measurement.

Influence of solar light on PFOA solubility in glass reactor

The prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard was added to the reactor, which had been previously washed with water. The standard solution was stirred in the dark for 30 minutes, after which solar light was introduced, and the solution was left for 3 hours. Samples were analyzed using LC-MS. The percentage difference between the PFOA concentrations in the first and last sample was calculated.

Table 7. Influence of solar light on PFOA solubility in glass reactor

Time /min	c(PFOA)/ ppm	Percentage difference
t=-30	0.09269	17.3236 %
t=0	0.09492	
t=60	0.09782	
t=180	0.11027	

It was confirmed that PFOA concentration increases with time under the solar light in the glass reactor.

Comparison of glass reactor and polypropylene beaker for conducting reactions with PFOA under solar light

Eighty milliliters of the prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard were added to both the glass reactor and the polypropylene beaker, which had been previously washed with water. The standard solution was stirred in the dark for 30 minutes, after which solar light was introduced, and the solution was left for 5 hours. Samples were analyzed using LC-MS. The percentage differences between the PFOA concentrations in the first and last samples were calculated.

Table 8. Comparison of glass reactor and PP beaker under the solar light

Time	Glass rect. c(PFOA)/ ppm	Percentage difference	PP beaker c(PFOA)/ ppm	Percentage difference
t=-30	0.08708	19.0921 %	0.08675	11.5769 %
t=0	0.08694		0.08831	
t= 60	0.09168		0.09039	
t=120	0.0941		0.09163	
t=180	0.09741		0.09481	
t=240	0.1021		0.09663	
t=300	0.10546		0.09741	

The results demonstrated that the PFOA concentration increased to a greater extent in the glass reactor compared to the polypropylene beaker.

Stirring and solar light effect on the PFOA concentration

Eighty milliliters of the prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard were added to four polypropylene beakers, each treated as follows: The first beaker was covered with foil and left undisturbed. The second beaker was covered with foil and stirred at 500 rpm. The third beaker was left uncovered, not stirred, and placed under solar light after 30 minutes, where it remained for an additional 60 minutes. The fourth beaker was also left uncovered and placed under solar light after 30 minutes, remaining there for 60 minutes, with continuous stirring at 500 rpm throughout the duration. Samples were analyzed using LC-MS. The percentage differences between the PFOA concentrations in the first and last samples were calculated.

Table 9. Stirring and solar light effect on the PFOA concentration (90 minute experiment)

PP Beakers – time /min	c(PFOA) /ppm	Percentage difference
Closed not stir. t=0	0.09796	(-) 2.42806 %
Closed not stir. t=30	0.09749	
Closed not stir. t=90	0.09561	
Closed stir. t=0	0.09822	0.58877 %
Closed stir. t=30	0.09950	
Closed stir. t=90	0.09880	
Open not stir. t=0	0.09664	4.30314 %
Open not stir. t=30	0.09727	
Open not stir. t=90 (light t=60)	0.10089	
Open stir. t=0	0.09474	4.95136 %
Open stir. t=30	0.09757	
Open stir. t=90 (light t=60)	0.09955	

The most significant increase in concentration was observed in the beaker that was both stirred and exposed to solar light. These results indicate that exposure to light resulted in a greater increase in PFOA concentration compared to stirring.

To further validate the results, an additional experiment was conducted. Eighty milliliters of the prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard were added to two polypropylene beakers. The first beaker was stirred for 5 hours in the dark, while the second beaker was stirred at 500 rpm and simultaneously exposed to solar light for 5 hours. Samples were analyzed using LC-MS. The percentage differences between the PFOA concentrations in the first and last samples were then calculated.

Table 10. Stirring and solar light effect on the PFOA concentration (300 minute experiment)

Time /min	Dark c(PFOA) /ppm	Percentage difference	Light c(PFOA) /ppm	Percentage difference
t=0	0.08863	3.29579 %	0.08729	7.34937 %
t= 60	0.08985		0.09015	
t=120	0.09089		0.09084	
t=180	0.08980		0.09075	
t=240	0.09149		0.09067	
t=300	0.09160		0.09395	

It was confirmed that both stirring and exposure to light contributed to an increase in PFOA concentration over time. Additionally, it was observed that the combination of stirring and light exposure resulted in a greater increase in PFOA concentration compared to stirring alone.

Influence of stirring speed on PFOA concentration

Eighty milliliters of the prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard were added to three polypropylene beakers, each of which was stirred for 3 hours at different speeds: 300, 600, and 900 rpm. The samples were then analyzed using LC-MS, and the percentage differences between the PFOA concentrations in the first and last samples were calculated.

Table 11. Influence of stirring speed on PFOA concentration

Stirring speed – time /min	c(PFOA) /ppm	Percentage difference
300 rpm t=0	0.08954	0.223115 %
300 rpm t=60	0.0908	
300 rpm t=120	0.08764	
300 rpm t=180	0.08974	
600 rpm t=0	0.08704	3.03236 %
600 rpm t=60	0.08811	
600 rpm t=120	0.08981	
600 rpm t=180	0.08972	
900 rpm t=0	0.0896	2.93616 %
900 rpm t=60	0.09097	
900 rpm t=120	0.09438	
900 rpm t=180	0.09227	

At a stirring speed of 300 rpm, no significant change in PFOA concentration was observed. However, at stirring speeds of 600 and 900 rpm, an approximately 3% increase in concentration was observed, with both speeds showing similar results.

Effect of temperature on PFOA concentration

Eighty milliliters of the prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard were added to a polypropylene beaker, which was then placed on a magnetic stirrer with temperature control. Initially, the temperature was set to 30°C for one hour, after which it was increased by 5°C every hour. Throughout the experiment, the solution was stirred at a constant speed of 300 rpm. The samples were analyzed using LC-MS, and the percentage difference was calculated for each step of the temperature change, as well as the total percentage difference between the first and the final sample.

Table 12. Effect of gradual change in temperature on PFOA concentration

Time /min	Temperature /°C	c(PFOA) /ppm	Percentage difference	
t=0	28 (RT)	0.08033	/	9.79104 %
t=60	30	0.08089	0.694703 %	
t=120	35	0.08397	3.7365 %	
t=240	45	0.0886	5.36594 %	

The results indicate that temperature significantly influences the increase in PFOA concentration.

An additional experiment was conducted in which 80 milliliters of the prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard were added to three polypropylene beakers. Each beaker was stirred at 300 rpm and maintained at different temperatures: 30°C, 35°C, and 40°C. The samples were then analyzed using LC-MS, and the percentage differences between the PFOA concentrations in the first and final samples were calculated.

Table 13. Effect of temperature on PFOA concentration

Time /min	Temperature /°C	c(PFOA) /ppm	Percentage difference
t=0	30	0.09248	0.04324 %
t=60	30	0.09216	
t=180	30	0.09220	
t=240	30	0.09252	
t=0	35	0.09099	2.73171 %
t=60	35	0.09021	
t=180	35	0.09450	
t=240	35	0.09351	
t=0	40	0.09013	3.44564 %
t=60	40	0.09190	
t=120	40	0.09329	

The most significant increase in concentration was observed in the beaker maintained at 40°C. It should be noted that the solution was held at this temperature for the shortest duration.

Effect of reactor washing solvent

The prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard was added to the reactor, which had been thoroughly washed with a 50:50 methanol-water solution. The standard solution was stirred in the dark for 30 minutes, after which solar light was introduced, and the solution was left exposed for 3 hours. The samples were analyzed using LC-MS, and the percentage difference between the PFOA concentrations in the first and final samples was calculated. The results were then compared with those obtained from a similar experiment conducted in a reactor that had been washed with water only.

Table 14. Effect of reactor washing solvent

Time /min	MeOH:H ₂ O c(PFOA)/ ppm	Percentage difference	H ₂ O c(PFOA)/ ppm	Percentage difference
t=-30	0.08111	8.66899 %	0.09269	17.3236 %
t=0	0.0798		0.09492	
t=60	0.0855		0.09782	
t=180	0.08846		0.11027	

It was observed that the increase in PFOA concentration was significantly lower when the reactor was washed with a methanol-water solution, compared to when it was washed with water alone.

To confirm the results, additional experiment was performed. The prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard was added to the reactor, which had been thoroughly washed with a 50:50 methanol-water solution. The standard solution was stirred in the dark for 30 minutes, after which solar light was introduced, and the solution was left exposed for 3 hours. Each time samples were taken in triplicates and analyzed using LC-MS. Percentage difference between the PFOA concentration in the first and final sample was calculated.

Table 15. Effect of reactor washing solvent tested with sample triplicates

Time /min	c(PFOA) /ppm	Average c(PFOA) /ppm	Percentage difference
t=-30	0.10031	0.09986	9.17256 %
t=-30	0.09885		
t=-30	0.10043		
t=0	0.0978	0.09775	
t=0	0.0993		
t=0	0.09615		
t=90	0.10372	0.10405	
t=90	0.10499		
t=90	0.10345		
t=180	0.10895	0.10946	
t=180	0.10825		
t=180	0.11117		

It was confirmed that the increase in PFOA concentration is significantly lower when the reactor is washed with a methanol-water solution, compared to when it was washed with water alone.

Evaporation influence on PFOA concentration

The prepared 0.1 ppm PFOA standard was added to the reactor, which had been thoroughly washed with a 50:50 methanol-water solution and additionally wiped with acetone. The standard solution was stirred in the dark for 30 minutes, after which solar light was introduced, and the solution was left exposed for 4 hours. The experiment was performed twice: first, with the reactor covered with a glass plate, and second, with the reactor left open. The samples were analyzed using LC-MS, and the percentage difference between the PFOA concentrations in the first and final samples was calculated.

Table 16. Evaporation influence on PFOA concentration

Time /min	Covered (PFOA)/ ppm	Percentage difference	Not covered c(PFOA)/ ppm	Percentage difference
t=-30	0.09117	5.09861 %	0.09112	4.29553 %
t=0	0.09286		0.09065	
t=60	0.0944		0.0933	
t=120	0.09369		0.09342	
t=180	0.09522		0.09351	
t=240	0.09594		0.09512	

Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that solvent evaporation does not have an impact on the increase in PFOA concentration.

Ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography – tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS)

The concentration of PFOA was monitored using the ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with a triple quadrupole mass spectrometry LCMS-8050 (Shimadzu, Japan). The modular system consists of LC part: controller, SCL-40, degasser, DGU-405, two pumps, LC-40Dx3, autosampler, SK-40Cx3, column thermostat, CTO-40S (all Shimadzu, Japan); the MS parts were: mass spectrometer LCMS-8050 (Shimadzu, Japan) and nitrogen generator Genius 1051 PSA (Peak Scientific, UK). All samples were filtered before analysis (Chromafil, Xtra CA, 0.45 μm , Macheray Nagel, Germany) and analysed in triplicates.

Chromatographic separation of PFOA was done on a Shimpack GIST (Shimadzu, Japan) C18 column with dimensions of 150 mm x 2.1 mm, 3 μm (Shimadzu, Japan). The column was thermostated on 40 °C. Ammonium acetate (20 mM) in ultrapure water (phase A) and methanol (phase B) at a flow rate of 0.4 mL min⁻¹ in the 70:30 ratio, was used as the mobile phase for separation, analysed in isocratic mode for 10 min. Injection volume was 5 μL .

The collision energy was 20 eV. Nitrogen was used as nebulizing and drying gas, while flow was 3 L min⁻¹ and 5 L min⁻¹ respectively. Argon was used as heating (collision) gas and flow was 15 L/min. Interface temperature was 190 °C, desolvation line temperature was 200 °C, while the heating block temperature was 300 °C. Molecular ion with a mass of 413 Da [M-H]⁻ was recorded in the first quadrupole (Q1) in the negative operating mode, while in the second quadrupole the characteristic ions of the molecular ion fragments were recorded, while tracked multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) transitions were 413→369, 413→219 and 413→169 m/z.

Ion chromatography (IC)

Ion chromatographic analysis was performed using a one-dimensional analytical IC system, the Dionex ICS-3000 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The entire system was controlled using the Chromeleon 7.1 software package. A hydroxide ion solution (KOH) was used as the mobile phase, with isocratic elution conducted at 30 mM KOH. The flow rate was maintained at 1 mL/min, with the column temperature set at 30 °C and the detector temperature at 35 °C. The injection loop volume was 25 μL . The stationary phase consisted of a high-capacity ion-exchange column (AS11 HC) paired with a guard column (AG11 HC). Detection of PFOA was performed using a conductivity detector. Nitrogen gas of 5.0 purity was used as an inert gas to prevent vacuum formation in the mobile phase reservoirs. An ASRS 4 mm electrolytic

suppressor was used to suppress the mobile phase signal, with the current set at 75 mA. The analysis time for each sample was 10 minutes.

1.2 PFOA by Ionic chromatography

Instrument details

The instrument is an Integrion (Thermo Scientific), with a conductivity detector. We use a Dionex IonPac AS11-HC column. The mobile phase is KOH, prepared with a MilliQ ultrafiltered water eluent generator.

Pollutant details

PFOA (Perfluorooctanoic acid, CAS # 1763-23-1)	
Molecular Formula:	C ₈ HF ₁₅ O ₂
Formula Weight:	414.07 g/mol
Composition:	C(23.21%) H(0.24%) F(68.82%) O(7.73%)
Density:	1.745 ± 0.06 g/cm ³
Polarizability:	17.00 ± 0.5 10 ⁻²⁴ cm ³
Structural formula:	

Reactor details

The reactor consisted of an aluminum chassis equipped with three low-pressure Hg lamps (Actinic BL, 15W, Philips) and two small fans on the lid as well as a magnetic stirrer, hence providing a top-down height-adjustable illumination. The aliquots taken were centrifuged (11000 rpm for 2 min) to remove the solid contents and analyzed by IC described above.

Photocatalytic activity was also assessed in an annular batch reactor of volume 50 mL. The same lamps were used in vertical position and the reactor was mixed using a top-down mixing rod at 300 rpm (IKA). The mixing of the system was provided by purging with O₂ or N₂ at 25 mL/min from the bottom of the cell.

2. Removal of PFOA by UVA/photocatalytic system using carbon-nitride based photocatalysts

Adsorption study

Prior to degradation studies were conducted studies of adsorption of fluoride ions onto several common materials found as the laboratory glassware. We conducted the experiments in glass beakers and found high degree of adsorption of fluoride ions on the glass walls. We then proceeded with experiments done in polypropylene plastic (PP) bottles due to lower adsorption of F^- onto this material. The table below shows this results. Clearly, the catalysts adsorb quite a lot of fluoride ions, hence the final measured concentrations of F^- is most probably an underestimation of the real concentration.

NaF mass conc. ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Catalyst	Mass conc. of catalyst [g/L]	Time of adsorption t [h]	F^- ions [μg] at $t = 0$	F^- ions [μg] at $t =$ t
95	S3N2	0,5	24	97	15 \pm 5
165	S3N2	0,5	24	165	51,84

Photocatalytic testing results

Two most promising materials were tested for their photocatalytic degradation of PFOA which was monitored by following defluorination of the parent molecule. The first material was graphitic carbon nitride nanospheres calcined under N_2 atmosphere either in tubular furnace (TB) or in the microwave furnace (MW), named gCN in the table below. The second one was a nano- TiO_2 material doped with sulphur (S) and nitrogen (N), named S3N2 in the table below. The third material was activated carbon (AC).

In the table the first 24 experiments were done in borosilicate glassware (marked with a line) while from then on the experiments were conducted in PP plastic.

Experim.	Pollutant	Mass conc. of pollutant	Catalyst	Mass conc. of catalyst [g/L]	Time t [h] (incl. 1h of adsorption)	F ⁻ ions [μg] at $t = 0$	F ⁻ ions [μg] at $t = t$
S1	PFOA	1 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	-	-
S2	PFOA	10 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	-	-
S3	PFOA	50 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	7,01	6,51
S4	PFOA	100 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	-	-
S5	PFOS	1 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	4,99	6,004
S6	PFOS	10 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	4,99	6,5
S7	PFOS	50 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	5,5	6,004
S8	PFOS	100 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	4,99	5,5
S9	PFOA	100 μg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	24	-	-
S10	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2 + 1% Pt	0,5	4	3,48	7,19
S12	PFOA	5 mg/L	gCN-TB-Etch	0,5	4	3,48	6,82
S13	PFOA	5 mg/L	AC/PS	0,5	4	-	-
S14	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2+1% Pt	0,5	24	8,79	130,96
S15	PFOA	5 mg/L	gCN-TB-Etch	0,5	24	8,79	13,71
S16	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2+1% Pt	0,5	18	-	16,16
S17	PFOA	5 mg/L	gCN-TB-Etch	0,5	18	-	6,59
S18	PFOA	5 mg/L	gCN-MW-Etch+1%Ag	0,5	6	-	0
S19	PFOA	5 mg/L	gCN-TB-Etch+1%Ag	0,5	18	-	0
S20	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2	0,5	22	2,3	20,86
S21	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2+1% Pt	0,5	22	2,3	16,84
S22	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2+1% Ag	0,5	22	1,3	10,83
S23	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2+1% Pt	0,5	22	2,5	18,52
S24	PFOA+NaF*	5 mg/L	S3N2	0,5	72	93,19	13
S25	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2	0,5	72	0	12,52
S26	PFOA	40 mg/L	S3N2+1% Pt	0,5	72	1,73	6265,97
S27**	PFOA	40 mg/L	S3N2+1% Pt	0,5	72	1,73	6009,61
S28	PFOA	5 mg/L	S3N2	0,5	24	0,68	75,18

*NaF concentration = 95 μg/L.

**Experiment carried out in a box reactor; other experiments: vertical annular reactor.

Because we could not observe any measurable release of fluoride ions under environmental concentrations of PFOA (1, 10, 50, and 100 $\mu\text{g/L}$) we opted for higher PFOA initial concentration of 5 mg/L . Additionally, even higher 40 mg/L experiments were done (the table numbers S26 and S27).

Figure 1. Calibration curve for IC based on the aqueous concentration of NaF. All lab equipment was made of PP.

Figure 2. Temporal kinetics of fluoride formation during the irradiation of sample S₃N₂-1% Pt with UVA lamps for up to 3 days. The top plot shows the theoretical F⁻ concentration if PFOA was completely defluorinated. The data in the bottom plot is fitted to a sigmoidal curve showing a lag phase in the beginning and an equilibrium concentration of F⁻ at the final hours of the experiment. Experimental conditions: c(catalyst) = 0.5 g/L, max. irradiation wavelength = 365 nm.

Degradation of PFOA by BiVO₄-based catalysts under solar irradiation; part of paper with status “*in preparation*” with foreseen submission date in December 2024 to *Molecules* journal with tentative title:

Elucidating semiconducting properties and photocatalytic performance of surface-decorated BiVO₄ for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern

Authors: *Marin Popović, Suresh Kumar Pandey, Josipa Papac Zjačić, Vladimir Dananić, Marijana Kraljić Roković, Marin Kovačić, Hrvoje Kušić, Andraž Šuligoj, Urška Lavrenčič Štangar, Ana Lončarić Božić*

Figure 5. Degradation profiles of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using different photocatalytic materials: pristine BiVO₄, Ag-BiVO₄ and Ag-Fe-BiVO₄, as well as hydrolysis and photolysis under studied conditions: solar light, natural pH (5.5), $\gamma(\text{catalyst})=1$ g/L (where applicable)

Degradation of PFOA by SnS₂-TiO₂ catalyst under solar irradiation; part of paper with status “*in preparation*” with foreseen submission date in January 2025 to *Catalyst* journal with tentative title:

Degradation of PFOA by SnS₂-TiO₂ photocatalyst in the presence of sulfite

Authors: Suresh Kumar Pandey, Josipa Papac Zjačić, Sandra Romac, Marijana Kraljić Roković, Marin Kovačić, Hrvoje Kušić, Boštjan Žener, Boštjan Genorio, Urška Lavrenčič Štangar, Ana Lončarić Božić

Conditions:

PFOA Conc.: 5 ppm
Catalyst dose: 1 mg/mL
Sulfite Conc.: 1 mM

Light source: **Solar light**
30 min dark + 240 min under solar

pH	Time (min)	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)/Na ₂ SO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₃	Photolysis	pH	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)/Na ₂ SO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₃
Natural pH	-30	5,85	4,42	4,22	----	pH 8	5,77	7,6	6,93
	0	8,6	5,71	5,83	5,12		7,83	8,8	8,6
	60	7,53	5,91	5,28	6,77		7,67	8,61	8,72
	120	5,1	4,3	6,13	7,16		7,58	8,77	8,77
	180	7,12	6,1	6,14	7,08		7,63	8,88	8,87
	240	7,24	6,06	6,36	7,24		5,96	8,95	8,99

Conditions:

PFOA Conc.: 5 ppm
Catalystdose: 1 mg/mL
SulfiteConc.: 1 mM

Light source: UVC
30 min dark + 240 min under UVC

pH	Time (min)	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)/Na ₂ SO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₃	Photolysis	pH	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)	SnS ₂ -TiO ₂ (20%)/Na ₂ SO ₃	Na ₂ SO ₃
Natural pH	-30	4,62	4,91	5,78	----	pH 8	5,27	6,93	7,11
	0	7,19	6,44	6,56	4,47		7,47	8,88	8,8
	60	3,21	4,28	2,88	2,58		4,14	6,66	3,51
	120	-3,31	2,37	0,06	-0,28		1,25	3,46	-0,32
	180	-2,11	-3,78	-2,52	-2,75		-0,71	1,42	-2,18
	240	-2,96	-2,05	-3,63	-3,98		----	-0,41	-3,75

$$\text{Defluorination ratio (\%)} = \frac{C_{F^-}}{C_0 \times 15} \times 100$$

Where, C_{F^-} and C_0 are the concentration of fluoride ions and initial concentration of PFOA.

Conditions:

PFOA Conc.: 5 ppm

Catalyst dose: 1 mg/mL

30 min dark + 240 min under UVC

Sample	Defluorination ratio (%)	
	In solar	In UVC
SnS ₂ /TiO ₂ (20%)	NA	0.073
SnS ₂ /TiO ₂ (20%) + Na ₂ SO ₃	NA	0.085
Na ₂ SO ₃	0.0075	0.237
PFOA (photolysis)	NA	0.192

Sample	Defluorination ratio (%)
SnS2-TiO2+UVC	0.023
Photolysis (UVC)	0.035

Testing of new synthesized materials for PFOA degradation under solar irradiation

Figure 6. Degradation profiles of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using different photocatalytic materials: SrTiO₃ and N-SrTiO₃ as well as hydrolysis and photolysis under studied conditions: solar light, natural pH (5.5), $\gamma(\text{catalyst})=1$ g/L (where applicable)

Figure 7. Degradation profiles of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using ZnSe as well as hydrolysis and photolysis under studied conditions: solar light, natural pH (5.5), $\gamma(\text{catalyst})=1$ g/L (where applicable)

Figure 8. Degradation profiles of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using CuGaS₂ as well as hydrolysis and photolysis under studied conditions: solar light, natural pH (5.5), $\gamma(\text{catalyst})=1$ g/L (where applicable)

Figure 9. Degradation profiles of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using different photocatalytic materials: Cu₂O, Ag₃PO₄, and Ag₃PO₄/Cu₂O as well as hydrolysis and photolysis under studied conditions: solar light, natural pH (5.5), $\gamma(\text{catalyst})=1 \text{ g/L}$ (where applicable)

Figure 10. Degradation profiles of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) using different photocatalytic materials: WO₃ and ZnWO₄ as well as hydrolysis and photolysis under studied conditions: solar light, natural pH (5.5), $\gamma(\text{catalyst})=1$ g/L (where applicable)